

Experimental Characterization of sub-THz Wireless Communications Building Blocks on a Silicon Platform

(Student paper)

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In the evolution of RF photonics, silicon photonics is an important enabling technology providing high-performance devices. Here, we introduce key building blocks for a sub-THz prototype wireless transmitter utilizing Tower's PH18MA Silicon photonics platform including: single-ring resonators, 10x5 array waveguide grating and Mach-Zehnder modulators.

Keywords: Silicon Photonics (SiPh), RF Photonics, Array Waveguide Grating, Ring Resonators, Mach Zehnder Modulator

INTRODUCTION

Silicon Photonics (SiPh) technology is experiencing a rapid development in the past two decades, evolving to a mature photonic integration platform hosting multiple key building blocks onto a single silicon chip. It is expected to become an enabler for next-generation high-speed communications as well as sensor applications, such as light detection and ranging (LIDAR). One of SiPh's strongest features is its compatibility with industrial CMOS to unlock photonic-electronic convergence [1]. Currently, a variety of SiPh technology platforms offer Multi-Project Wafer (MPW) services, which enables cost-effective access to the foundry services. The first MPW runs were offered through the ePIXfab service, which included IMEC and CEA-Leti foundries. TOWER Semiconductor, a silicon foundry specializing in Radio Frequency and High-Performance Analog and CMOS technology, introduced photonics into its platform, which has sparked high interest in RF Photonics applications.

Figure 1 depicts a schematic of the building blocks for a high-speed RF Photonics transmitter that is based on an external Optical Frequency Comb (OFC) offering phase-locked and constant mode-spacing, a high-speed photodiode, and a single SiPh chip as the key component of optical heterodyne RF Photonics transmission. The integrated components on the SiPh chip are optical wavelength selectors, optical modulators, and wavelength combiners. In this paper, we design and experimentally demonstrate the performance of SiPh key building blocks towards a monolithically integrated optical heterodyne system including:

- Optical filters, based in micro-ring resonators (MRRs), offering high wavelength selectivity to isolate individual wavelengths from an OFC, large free spectral ranges (FSRs) and high extinction ratios [2],
- Optical wavelength combiners, based on array waveguide grating (AWG) multiplexer/demultiplexer.
- Optical modulators, based on Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) structures, which offer high-performance optical modulation enabling higher-order modulation formats reaching 100Gb/s [3].

Figure 1 – An Illustration of the sub-THz wireless transmitter featuring MRR-based filtering, an AWG wavelength multiplexing and data modulation via MZM.

The Photonic integrated circuits (PICs) are integrated monolithically utilizing Tower's PH18MA Silicon photonics platform, which offers the 180 nm SOI process technology. The dimensions of the chips are 5 x 5 mm, resulting in an extremely compact optical circuit. The tested building blocks from this MPW submission were created and optimized using Synopsys OptoCompiler Platform and Photonic IC Design Flow.

DEVICE DESCRIPTIONS

Optical modulation and filtering are crucial functions in microwave photonics signal processing, important in optical heterodyne generation. Considering this application, we demonstrate silicon ring resonators with an FSR at 100 GHz and AWG-based wavelength multiplexing structure with 50 GHz channel spacing. A ring resonator-based wavelength selector has a length of 713.8 μm and a phase-shifter (PS) of 266.68 μm on top of it, to ensure maximum tunability of the FSR. In addition, the tested AWG structure has 10 inputs and 5 outputs, with each input introduced in a phase shifter-based MZM, having a total length of 2000 μm , utilizing the electro-optic effect. Hence, relying on the plasma dispersion effect, the optical path can be altered via applied voltage. Also, grating couplers (GCs) of 18 μm diameter and maximum coupling angle at 8° are used in all the inputs and the outputs of the structures.

Figure 2- Illustration of the a) Experimental setup for the passive and active characterization of single-ring resonators, AWG and the MZM, respectively. b) single-MRR with GCs of 18 μm diameter (left), and c) 10x5 AWG structure utilizing the same GCs.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We report the spectral responses of the optical filtering based on the single-ring resonator structure and of the AWG-based multiplexing, operating in the C-band. Fig. 1(a) displays the characterization setup that has been deployed for the passive and active characterization of the optical components. The recording transmission spectra of the silicon RRs is recorded using an optical amplifier, Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) at the input and the Optical Spectrum Analyzer (OSA) to detect the spectral response at the drop port. Light is coupled and measured on the MRR structure through lensed fibers of 5 μm spot size in both input/output GCs. For the characterization of AWG structure, we conducted a die-scale test. The chip is placed on a copper chuck under temperature control close to 23°C . The optical testing was done manually using an 8° angled facet fiber array with a pitch of 250 μm . The fiber array is placed on a custom angled fiber array holder and mounted on a set of translation stages to form a 5-axis translation stage system.

Both of the spectral responses can be observed in Fig. 3(a). The response shaping of the micro-ring resonator at the drop port shows that the FSR is around 97 GHz, very close to the simulation value of 100 GHz. Also, the through transmission spectra of the resonator is measured and is reconciled well with the drop port. At the resonance wavelength of 1.55 μm , the following key parameters have been calculated for the assessment of MRR-based filters: FWHM is equal to 0.18 nm, the -3dB bandwidth is 16 GHz (0.1283 nm) and the Q-factor is $8.61 \cdot 10^3$. In the following step, the optical response of the AWG is measured for the two input center channels. Thus, measuring the response of the AWG's input centered channels 3 and 8, the maximum output optical power can be obtained from the center channel 3 at the output. As we can see in Fig. 3(a), there is a repetitive response from both of the channels with FSR of 463.5 GHz. Also, the channel spacing between channel 3 and 8 is 225 GHz, and the FWHM is 0.28 nm, which both are in good agreement with the simulated values. The generated side modes of each individual channel are caused probably from the internal reflections between GCs and AWG input/output and the chip facet. Therefore, it's under investigation to define precisely the origin of the noise between the resonant responses. Additionally, crosstalk between the waveguides can affect the performance, which depends on the quality of the fabrication process, device size, channels number and spacing, etc. However, waveguide fabrication imperfections are mainly responsible for the crosstalk increase.

Next, the electro-optic modulation response of the MZM is measured. Since the modulator has lumped electrodes as contact pads, a DC probe needles were used for RF signal injection. This is the reason why, as shown in Figure 3 (b), only a maximum data rate of 4 Gbit/s was successfully transmitted. For the testing of the MZM, 1550 nm light is coupled from an optical source of 10 dBm optical power into the GC. The MZM optical transmission response is captured by sweeping the DC voltage injected into one of the MZM arms from 0 to -14 V. We have recorded a RF π voltage (V_{π}) that is equal to -9 V and the quadrature transmission point at -3.6 V. Considering this, the voltage-length product is calculated at 1.8 V-cm, for a 2 mm modulation length. For the data transmission test, pseudo-random bit sequence (PRBS) with a length of 2^7-1 was used as the driving signal followed by an RF amplifier. The modulator is biased at quadrature transmission point. The optical output signal is amplified up to 10 dBm with an EDFA and then is detected by a single-ended photodiode (PD). Finally, a bit-error rate tester (BERT) is used for BER computing and eye-diagram analysis. The recorded eye-diagrams are shown in Fig. 3(b) for data rates of 1.5, 3, 4 and 4.5 Gbps. By optimizing the design of the MZM and by using traveling-wave electrodes instead of lumped electrodes, higher data rates can be achieved.

Figure 3 - a) Transmission spectra of the single-MRR at the drop port and of the AWG from the filtered center channels 3 and 8. b) Eye diagrams measured at a received power of -45 dBm for (i) 1.5 Gbps, (ii) 3 Gbps, (iii) 4 Gbps and (iv) 4.5 Gbps data transmission.

DISCUSSION

We have demonstrated a sub-THz wireless transmitter, achieving transmission data up to 4 Gbps. Monolithically integrated elements have recorded an FSR of almost 100 GHz from a micro-RR and a 225 GHz spacing between the AWG's center input channels. The reported performance of these building blocks proves that a complete optical processing fully-functional system can be miniaturized on-chip on the silicon platform.

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